

Detection of Buildings with Potential Damage Using Differential Deformation Maps

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The European Ground Motion Service (EGMS) is a crucial component of the systematic monitoring and quantification of land displacement across Europe. By using Sentinel-1 full-resolution images, EGMS offers a reliable, consistent, and annually updated dataset for detecting natural and anthropogenic ground motion phenomena. While the Copernicus platform grants free accessibility to EGMS displacement maps containing a massive number of measurement points, the challenge lies in finding appropriate methodologies and tools to make this wealth of information easily exploitable, especially to non-experts. This study leverages the EGMS displacement maps to display the capability of a novel software tool designed for the automatic identification of urban structures that may be susceptible to damage due to differential movements. This approach is notable since it can be applied to areas of any size, from local to national scale, and while designed for EGMS data, it can be applied to any other InSAR-derived displacement maps, regardless of the data source. Despite prior researches on differential settlements, this study concentrates on analysing every single buildings and computing the spatial gradient of deformation by using Measurement Points specifically associated with each building. The designed software tool quickly analyses and detects at-risk buildings, applying a classification system that categorizes them based on the severity of their spatial deformation gradient, with uncertainty as the primary factor, and generates a differential deformation map as a result. The Monte Carlo simulations assisted us in estimating the standard deviation of the spatial gradient, which was determined to be $0.05 \text{ (mm}\times\text{yr}^{-1}\times\text{m}^{-1}\text{)}$. The approach was tested with EGMS data over the area of Barcelona Municipality (Spain) from 2017 to 2021. The complete source code is available at <https://github.com/saeedehshahbazi/detecting-differential-deformation.git>. In addition, a COSMO-SkyMed dataset was used to assess and appraise its performance. The number of detected buildings was 149 in the EGMS dataset and 155 in the

COSMO-SkyMed dataset, with approximately 50% of the buildings classified as Very-Low/Low in both datasets. The results demonstrate the technique's robustness, as it yielded consistent outcomes using distinct datasets. To verify the differential deformation map, a field survey was conducted to observe any evident structural damage (e.g., cracks or fractures). The differential deformation maps may represent a primary source of information for conducting a comprehensive analysis and vulnerability/risk assessment in urban areas. The effectiveness of this technique, as evidenced by consistent outcomes with diverse datasets, underlines its value in improving our understanding of structural vulnerabilities, thus contributing to informed urban management.

Keywords: EGMS, differential deformation, spatial gradient of deformation, Sentinel-1, COSMO-SkyMed, damage, measurement points

1. Introduction

Natural hazards such as landslides, subsidence, and earthquakes can have significant effects on urban areas. Furthermore, man-made operations such as construction, mining, and industrial activities can cause land deformation, posing risks to urban areas. These risks are high and complex to manage because they are often caused by interconnected phenomena and can lead to a series of effects (Corominas, et al. 2014, Botey i Bassols, et al. 2021). Urban managers and the scientific communities are particularly concern with this issue and focus on evaluating potential vulnerabilities. Through continuous monitoring and hazard identification, they can maintain effectiveness, which is reduce risks, and enhance environmental safety. In addition to traditional monitoring techniques, like topographic leveling, global navigation satellite system (GNSS), Differential Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (DInSAR) can provide useful information on displacement rate, derived from processing the SAR images. DInSAR is the most powerful tool for measuring small-scale deformation over large areas and the Persistent Scatterer Interferometry (PSI) techniques represent an advanced DInSAR class. PSI can maintain the full resolution of input

SAR images and is well suited for structures and infrastructure analysis and monitoring. It offers the advantage of sensitivity to small deformations, with a velocity precision of approximately 1 mm/yr (Crosetto, et al. 2016, Ferretti, et al. 2007). PSI has been successfully employed in several applications including the monitoring of various urban processes such as thermal deformation of buildings (Crosetto, et al. 2015, Monserrat, et al. 2011), subsidence in urban areas (Peduto, et al. 2017, Cigna and Tapete 2021, Ezquerro, et al. 2020), foundation settlement (Milillo, et al. 2016, Bozzano, et al. 2011, Stramondo, et al. 2008), and surface effects due to tunneling (Botey i Bassols, et al. 2021, Giardina, et al. 2019, Serrano-Juan, et al. 2017). The development of Advanced DInSAR (A-DInSAR) resulted in the creation of the European Ground Motion Service (EGMS), whose main objective is to provide consistent, accurate, and annually updated information about ground displacements related to both natural and anthropogenic phenomena over Europe. EGMS is a key part of the European Union's Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, and its data is useful to a wide range of users, including academic institutions, industry, and government agencies. The dataset is generated from the interferometric analysis of Sentinel-1 radar images at full resolution and includes a baseline product covering the period from February 2015 to the end of 2020, with annual updates afterward. These products include massive datasets with billions of displacement Measurement Points (MP), each point associated with a time series of displacement, while analysing them can be challenging and time-consuming.

In the field of damage and risk assessment of the buildings in urban areas, several studies have been worked including (Cascini, et al. 2013, Peduto, et al. 2017, Solari, et al. 2017, Zhu, et al. 2018). For instance, in Cascini et al. (2013), the authors proposed a methodology that integrates DInSAR data with a detailed analysis of damage documented through in situ surveys. Through analyzing the DInSAR data to assess damage to buildings/infrastructure caused by slow-moving

landslides, they demonstrated that measuring spatial variations in displacement could assist in evaluating the impact of motion-related phenomena and support urban management and planning efforts. Peduto et al. (2017) proposed a multi-scale approach for assessing building damage caused by differential settlements. They revealed that differential land movement can cause structural damage (e.g., fractures or wall cracks), whereas spatially uniform land movement has no immediate impact. They also investigated the role of soft soils in ground surface settlements and examined the spatial distribution and severity of building damage using damage surveys and DInSAR data. The approach generates empirical fragility curves for individual buildings, to assess the potential damage in urban areas.

After the availability of EGMS products, researchers began introducing EGMS to the public or implementing approaches using its products (Barra, et al. 2022, Mele, et al. 2023, Crosetto, et al. 2020). It is worth noting that extracting and utilizing such massive data required the development of new approaches and tools for automatically extracting information and providing initial interpretations. An example is given by the project RASTOOL (European ground motion risk assessment tool), which aims to develop semi-automatic methods and tools for extracting and deriving information from EGMS products as well as generating maps to aid hazards, exposure, and risk assessment. Barra et al. (2022) introduced EGMS and proposed an approach for generating a potential damage map for buildings/structures using the spatial gradient of deformation. This work proposed a methodology starting from the automatic detection of Active Deformation Areas (ADAs) to calculate the spatial gradients of displacements only within the extracted ADAs (Barra, et al. 2017). In this work, all the Measurements Points (MPs) within the ADAs were used to derive the spatial gradient maps and to attribute a potential damage class to the exposed buildings.

Starting from the previous work, this research proposes a methodology to exploit the EGMS displacement maps to identify buildings and urban structures that may be vulnerable to damage due to differential movements. The methodology works at a single-building scale, by automatically selecting the MPs that belong to the buildings and assessing the differential deformation (spatial gradient of deformation) affecting each specific building. This approach stands out for two primary reasons: first, it is not limited by the size of the area and can be used to analyze areas of any size, from a small village to a country. Second, although the methodology was specifically designed to utilize EGMS data, it can be seamlessly applied to any other PSI displacement data without complications. The methodology has been tested over the area of Barcelona (Spain) using two types of displacement maps. The first one contains the EGMS Sentinel-1 data (EGMS-S1) at medium resolution, while the second one was derived from the PSIG processing chain utilizing COSMO-SkyMed (PSIG-CSK) at high resolution. To validate the effectiveness of the proposed methodology, a field survey was conducted in one of the selected areas which involved examining the external damage, particularly cracks.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the building polygons data and the two distinct SAR datasets. Section 3 provides a detailed account of the process to generate differential deformation maps. Section 4 presents the experimental findings in the study area and an in-situ survey to verify the results. Finally, section 5 provides conclusions based on the work done.

2. Datasets

2.1. Buildings map

This research is centered in the municipality of Barcelona, Spain. The ESRI shapefile containing the building polygon is one of the key input data of the process. We used OpenStreetMap data that

includes a comprehensive collection of geographical features such as roads, buildings, parks, rivers, and points of interest. These aspects are represented as digital map layers, resulting in a comprehensive representation of the world's landscape (Hecht, et al. 2013). Noteworthy, OpenStreetMap is a free, editable map of the entire world that allows users to download urban coverage for the majority of countries in the world.

2.2. European Ground Motion Service data

The EGMS is part of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service's product portfolio and is implemented under the responsibility of the European Environment Agency. It uses Sentinel-1 satellite images and employs advanced Persistent Scatterer (PS) and Distributed Scatterer (DS) DInSAR processing techniques, along with a Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) model to calibrate the ground motion products. EGMS offers tools for visualization, analysis, and download of deformation products (EGMS white paper 2017). The key elements of EGMS were stated in the White Paper, available at <https://land.copernicus.eu/user-corner/technical-library/egms-white-paper>. The EGMS has three product levels. The first level, known as Basic, is made up of geocoded line of sight (LOS) deformation maps in ascending (ASC) and descending (DES) orbits, with measurements referencing a local point. The Calibrated is the second level which is a mosaic of the first level combined with GNSS data and the third level, Ortho, provides vertical and east-west deformation components resampled to a 100-m grid. Further information on the DInSAR methods used in EGMS is available in Ferretti et al. (2022) and Crosetto and Solari (2023). The EGMS Explorer allows the users to view, analyze data, and download the products. While the temporal resolution of EGMS data extends back to 2015, for the purpose of aligning it with CSK data in our study, we utilized the Basic EGMS product spanning 4.5 years, from April 2017 to October 2021 with a temporal sampling of one image every 6 days. The mean velocities

and displacements are estimated along the LOS direction. In order to cover the entire municipality of Barcelona, three bursts of EGMS-S1 in ASC geometry data were used (*EGMS_L2a_0132_0243_IW2*, *EGMS_L2a_0132-0244_IW2*, and *EGMS_L2a_0132_0245_IW2*).

2.3. COSMO Sky-Med data

A COSMO-SkyMed dataset was also utilized to generate a deformation map over the municipality of Barcelona. The results were compared with EGMS-S1 data to validate the proposed methodology and assess the differential deformation outcomes. We employed the PSI processing software PSIG (Devanry, et al. 2014) to process a collection of 50 Stripmap COSMO-SkyMed images in ASC geometry. The analyzed data is from April 2017 to October 2021, with a minimum temporal sampling of 4 days and a maximum temporal sampling of 168 days. The pixel footprint measures approximately 3 by 3 m. The main parameters of the PSIG-CSK and EGMS-S1 datasets are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters of Sentinel-1 and COSMO-SkyMed images

Dataset	PSIG-CSK	EGMS-S1
Acquisition mode	Stripmap: Himage	Interferometric Wide (IW) 2
Look Side	Right	Right
Wavelength [cm]	3.1	5.5
Polarization	HH	VV
Full resolution (azimuth/ground-range) [m]	3/3	14 /4
Orbit	Ascending	Ascending
Incidence angle	30° - 33°	37° – 39°
Period	April 2017 – October 2021	April 2017 – October 2021
Minimum revisit period [days]	4	6
Maximum revisit period [days]	168	60

Average revisit period [days]	32	7
Number of images	50	221

3. Methodology

3.1. Pre-Processing

The processing chain for deformation monitoring used in this study is the PSIG (Devanry, et al. 2014, Crosetto, et al. 2016), see the processing workflow in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Workflow of the PSIG procedure.

The PSIG includes the following main steps:

1. Interferogram generation. This includes the calibration of the images, image co-registration, and interferogram generation. The Digital Elevation Model (DEM) generated by NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) Global dataset (NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission, 2013), with 30 m resolution, was used. The generated interferograms were filtered using a high-pass Butterworth filter $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1+\left(\frac{\Omega}{\Omega_c}\right)^N}}\right)$

with a set of cutoff frequency (Ω_c) equal to 3 in order to remove the linear pattern of the images caused by orbital uncertainty.

Precise co-registration of the images based on the information provided by the orbits has been implemented.

2. Topographic error estimation. In this step, the points are selected based on the amplitude dispersion (DA). The selected points are then connected to form the interferogram network used for the topographic error estimation. A short temporal baseline with a maximum of 30 days was used for a better estimation of topographic error. From the original interferograms and the phase related to the topographic errors, we can generate the residuals.
3. Time series (TS) estimation. A Pixel-wise processing is performed iteratively, which analyses over time the unwrapped interferometric phases. An iterative least-squares method is used to compute the residuals and reject the outliers. After TS estimation, atmospheric errors are removed, and the deformation velocity for each point is calculated from the time series.
4. Geocoding of the results. Two important outputs are estimated from the mentioned steps: the annual linear velocity along the LOS direction, and the deformation time series.

The mean displacement velocity maps obtained over an area of Barcelona are shown in Figure 2. Note that EGMS-S1 displacement map exclusively represents an area that overlaps with CSK data. Significant deformation is visible in the southern part of the area, whereas the middle and upper portions appear to be stable. The standard deviation of velocities is 1.0 and 0.73 mm/yr in EGMS-S1 and PSIG-CSK data, respectively.

Figure 2: The displacement maps over the area of Barcelona with EGMS-S1 and PSIG-CSK datasets between 2017, and 2021.

3.2 Proposed methodology

In this research, a novel tool was developed to generate a differential deformation map for buildings and structures. The proposed methodology considers the spatial gradient (S-gradient) of deformation as the main factor causing buildings' damage and then categorizes buildings into different groups based on their potential for damage. Since this strategy's main goal is to identify susceptible buildings and urban structures, it exclusively considers individual buildings and their displacement data. However, it is important to note that this approach is limited to cases where sufficient MPs for a given building are available. In order to obtain the MPs corresponding to

building polygons, we conducted spatial intersections of points with building polygons; if the number of MPs is adequate, the building is selected for S-gradient calculation otherwise, it is excluded. For computing the S-gradient and to finding at-risk buildings, we required a parameter indicating displacement. Although the time series of each MP can serve as an important measure of deformation over time, in this investigation we have chosen to utilize the deformation velocity (rate of deformation) as it offers a stable and precise assessment of deformation. The flowchart of the proposed methodology is depicted in Figure 3 and is explained below. The source code used for the data processing and analysis in this study is available for public access. Details can be found in Section 8 (Data Availability).

3.2.1. Inputs

The necessary input data are 1) a displacement map of the study area, containing mean velocity, coordinates, and heights of MPs; and 2) an ESRI *shapefile* containing the polygon of buildings from OpenStreetMap.

Figure 3: Flow chart of proposed methodology.

3.2.2. Finding Measurement Points within Buildings

According to the proposed methodology, we intend to focus exclusively on the displacement information associated with buildings/structures. For this reason, the MPs that intersect the building polygons are selected. To account for inaccuracies in MP positioning, a buffer is applied around the building polygon's perimeter. To define the buffer dimension, we consider the glocalization errors estimated by Larsen, et al. 2020. The geolocation process includes projecting the chosen MP onto a geographic or cartographic system. Several factors contribute

to errors in geolocation, including orbital data of reference images, the Digital Elevation Model (DEM), the correction for an estimated height of MPs, and optionally sub-pixel determination of the MP in range and azimuth (Crosetto and Solari 2023).

Assuming the uniform distribution of the azimuth position of the scattering phase center inside a pixel, the standard deviation of the azimuth localization error (σ_{az}) is about $1/\sqrt{12}$ of azimuth pixel spacing. The error in ground range localization (σ_{rg}) may be influenced by two factors. The first is due to an unknown MP phase center position within the pixel (as with azimuth error; $1/\sqrt{12}$ of range pixel spacing) and the second term is due to MP height error (σ_h) (Larsen, et al. 2020, Crosetto and Solari, Satellite Interferometry Data Interpretation and Exploitation: Case Studies from the European Ground Motion Service (EGMS) 2023). Larsen et al. (2020) describe the relationship between height standard deviation and temporal coherence in a specific number of images. The height error has been estimated to range between 1 m and 4 m. Considering the information provided by EGMS-S1 basic product's temporal coherence, number of used images, and height errors we employed Eq. 1 to determine the extent of the localization error ($\sigma_{localization}$),

$$\sigma_{localization} = \sqrt{\sigma_{az}^2 + \sigma_{rg}^2}. \quad (1)$$

Considering the pixel dimension of EGMS-S1 (azimuth and range) of 14 by 4 m with a height standard deviation of 2.1 m, $\sigma_{localization}$ is roughly 5 m. This value was then utilized as a buffer size surrounding each building to ensure proper MP selection. Similarly, $\sigma_{localization}$ for the PSIG-CSK, with a pixel dimension of 3 by 3 m and a height standard deviation of 0.7 m (Costantini, et al. 2014) was estimated to be roughly 2 m.

An issue arises when an MP is located on the shared wall between two adjacent buildings, especially in the central portion of Barcelona where buildings are closely situated. In such cases, we propose to duplicate the mentioned MP and assign it to both buildings.

Two additional criteria are employed for selecting MPs more accurately and to generate a more reliable result for each building.

- MPs are selected based on their height. This is accomplished using a Digital Terrain Model (DTM), which indicates the height (elevation) of the terrain. This map is available for download on OpenTopography website (Continental Europe Digital Terrain Model), with 30 m resolution. To confirm that the selected points pertain to the building, a threshold is established, and each MP height is checked individually with a threshold. The threshold is set by adding 4 m to the DTM height. When the MP height exceeds this threshold, it is considered a valid point for the building, conversely MPs height lower than threshold is considered uncertain, as they may belong to things around the building such as street facilities. This may affect the accuracy of gradient computation.
- In the analysis of MPs, it is necessary to identify and eliminate isolated MPs as well as outlier points affected by noise or other error sources. This enables more precise S-gradient computations. A point is considered isolated if no additional points are found within an identified radius circle. In addition, to detect outliers, we established a z-score threshold to determine how far each point varies from the mean, in terms of standard deviation. In particular, the velocity within a five-point neighbourhood is checked to see if the velocity difference exceeds the threshold and likely the threshold is sufficiently reliable after multiple tests. For example, unwrapping error can sometimes provide abnormal velocity values such as a positive value in an area undergoing significant subsidence. This can lead

to extremely high gradient values, which arise from an incorrect positive value. If this is the case, they are labelled as outlier/isolated points and subsequently excluded from the analysis. After finding MPs belonging to buildings, the tool starts to compute the S-gradient of deformation only for the buildings with at least five MPs, of which three must be active and have velocities greater than 3 mm/yr. These criteria facilitate the identification of buildings that are vulnerable to damage and also reduce the volume of data that needs to be taken into account. By implementing these conditions, the analysis is streamlined, and the accuracy of the results is improved.

3.2.3. Spatial Gradient Computation

According to the flowchart, this step computes the S-gradient of the deformation, which requires three stages: 1_Rasterizing: The initial phase involves rasterization due to the reliance of the gradient calculation algorithm on raster data format. Therefore, the entire area of each building polygon is gridded into a specific pixel size (in this case, we picked 8 m). Subsequently, interpolation methods come into play to estimate values for raster cells by leveraging the known values of adjacent points. These methods help to fill the gaps and provide a continuous representation of the data across the raster grid (Setianto and Triandini 2013). In this research, the Inverse Distance Weighting (*IDW*) interpolation technique is employed, based on the values of neighbouring MPs, meanwhile for pixels already containing MPs, the average velocity of the MPs is applied. 2_S-gradient Computation: The S-gradient of displacement velocity is the main parameter utilized to produce differential deformation maps. The algorithm calculates the S-gradient at one grid point by comparing the values of the eight surrounding points in a 3x3 matrix

(Horn 1981). Given a 3x3 matrix of velocity values (z), $\begin{bmatrix} z_1 & z_2 & z_3 \\ z_4 & z_5 & z_6 \\ z_7 & z_8 & z_9 \end{bmatrix}$, the algorithm estimates the

gradient spatially at the central grid cell (z_5) as the sum of the absolute values of the velocity

variation in the east-west direction ($\frac{\partial z}{\partial x}$) and north-south direction ($\frac{\partial z}{\partial y}$) based on following Eq. 2 and Eq. 3:

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial x} = \frac{[(z_1+2z_4+z_7)-(z_3+2z_6+z_9)]}{8*grid\ spacing} , \quad \frac{\partial z}{\partial y} = \frac{[(z_1+2z_2+z_3)-(z_7+2z_8+z_9)]}{8*grid\ spacing} , \quad (2)$$

$$Gradient = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial y}\right)^2} . \quad (3)$$

It's important to mention that instead of using a rise-over-run gradient calculation, Eq. 3 assumes that a plane surface can touch the surface at any point in the x and y direction to calculate the S-gradient of deformation (Horn 1981, Austin 2002). In our study, the S-gradient is expressed in magnitude with the unit of "mm×yr⁻¹×m⁻¹".

The S-gradient's orientation is termed "Aspect" and is calculated according to Eq.4 as follows:

$$Aspect = Arctan\left(\frac{\left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial x}\right)}{\left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial y}\right)}\right) \quad (4)$$

where it is measured clockwise in degrees from 0° to 360°, where 0° is north-facing, 90° is east-facing, 180° is south-facing, and 270° is west-facing. An aspect raster will typically result in several S-gradient direction classes (Horn 1981).

3_Spatial Gradient intensity classification: The intensity of the S-gradient of deformation is treated as a categorical variable, allowing us to categorize buildings into distinct categories according to their maximum S-gradient values, as described in Table 2. The classification system consists of five categories: "Not reliable," "Low," "Medium," "High," and "Very High." Each category defines a different range of S-gradient values, providing a clear representation of the severity levels of S-gradient observed in the dataset. It is worth noting that because the majority of buildings in both datasets have a similar range of deformation velocity, a single classification can be used in general.

Max S-gradient [$\text{mm}\times\text{yr}^{-1}\times\text{m}^{-1}$]	Intensity classes
0.00 – 0.05	Not reliable
0.05 – 0.15	Low
0.15 – 0.25	Medium
0.25 – 0.35	High
0.35 – 1.00	Very High

Table 2: S-gradient intensity classes

The S-gradient uncertainty is the primary factor in the classification at hand, as it serves as a threshold for assigning the first class. To obtain the S-gradient standard deviation, we propagated the errors through the model using Monte Carlo simulation. We considered that the error sources are in the displacement velocity and the positioning of MPs. The interpolation noise could affect the standard deviation of the S-gradient. However, as IDW places more weight on nearby points with known values, and also we used the exact values for these known points, the impact on the S-gradient standard deviation is expected to be minimal. Both (displacement velocity and the positioning) errors were generated from normal distributions, utilizing the standard deviations of displacement velocity and positioning (Bassoli, et al. 2023). The error distribution for displacement velocity was modeled as a Gaussian distribution with a standard deviation of 1 mm/yr and a mean of 0 mm/yr. Regarding the positioning errors, two other Gaussian distributions with a standard deviation of 2 m and 5 m for Easting and Northing directions were used (Larsen, et al. 2020, Crosetto and Solari 2023). A set of 200 Monte Carlo simulations was applied. The standard deviation of the S-gradient roughly is $0.05 \text{ mm}\times\text{yr}^{-1}\times\text{m}^{-1}$, which is estimated by using the average value of standard deviations derived from the S-gradients of all buildings. As a result, the first class is categorized as "*Not Reliable*" since it falls below the S-gradient standard deviation. The last class, on the other hand, is called "*Very High*" because the

S-gradient of $0.35 \text{ mm} \times \text{yr}^{-1} \times \text{m}^{-1}$ causes deformation of 8.75 mm over five years within a distance of 5 m (the typical space between two pillars in typical constructions).

3.2.4. Generation of Differential Deformation Map

The primary outcome of the procedure is the creation of a differential deformation map, presented as a shapefile. This file contains crucial details such as building IDs, coordinates, and various metrics related to the S-gradient, including maximum, mean, standard deviation, and orientation. To facilitate the visualization of the outcomes, it is recommended to use Geographic Information System (GIS) tools. Figure 4 illustrates the sequential steps involved in generating the building differential deformation map using EGMS-S1 data. Figure 4a displays the building polygon

Figure 4. Complete processing workflow. a) Building’s polygons and the MPs within a polygon as well as the displacement TS of a given point. b) Interpolated deformation velocity using the *IDW* method. c) The S-gradient of deformation. d) Differential deformation map of given building, with “*Medium*” intensity level.

sourced from OSM, with overlaid selected MPs within the buffer of the polygon. Figures 4b and 4c demonstrate the rasterization process utilizing the IDW interpolation method and subsequent S-gradient computation.

The pink oval in the southwest portion of the building indicates an area where there is differential movement, as evidenced by a visible pattern of S-gradient. Finally, Figure 4d depicts the differential deformation map for the specified building, highlighting the classification of S-gradient intensity as "*Medium*," given the maximum S-gradient of $0.18 \text{ mm} \times \text{yr}^{-1} \times \text{m}^{-1}$.

4. Experimental Results and Discussion

4.1. Building Differential Deformation Map

The proposed approach was applied to the municipality of Barcelona, which faces both natural and human-made hazards. The entire area of 1179 km^2 contains a total of 145043 buildings (polygons), and the total number of MPs inside them is 9744 and 10854 in EGMS-S1 and PSIG-CSK, respectively. Figures 5a and 5b provide visual representations of the differential deformation map for buildings, utilizing inputs from both EGMS-S1 and PSIG-CSK datasets. The brown polygons depict the entirety of buildings, and among them, a subset comprising 149 buildings from EGMS-S1 and 155 from PSIG-CSK has been identified as vulnerable to potential damage. These structures have been categorized based on their S-gradient intensity, ranging from "*Low*" to "*Very High*". As illustrated in Figure 5, the southern sector of the study area has the highest concentration of identified buildings. This phenomenon correlates with notable deformations occurring within this region, as indicated in Figure 2. Significant deformations are specifically observed in the Barcelona port, airport, and El Prat de Llobregat zone, in comparison to the relatively stable conditions that exist within the city of Barcelona.

The area of the smallest building that is detected is about 90 m² and 82 m² in EGMS-S1 and PSIG-CSK, respectively. Furthermore, the detected buildings have an average area of approximately 7000 m² in both datasets. Due to the large size of industrial buildings, they stand out as good candidates for efficient detection. Table 3 presents key statistics of both datasets.

Table 3. Some key statistics of EGMS-S1 and PSIG-CSK datasets

Item	EGMS-S1	PSIG-CSK
Total number of MPs	2,073,441	3,014,633
STD of points [mm/yr]	1.04	0.73
Number of detected buildings	149	155
Number of MPs inside buildings	9744	10852
Area of the smallest detected building [m ²]	96.6	82.2
The average area of detected buildings [m ²]	9441.2	6751.9
Percentage of buildings classified as “not reliable”	21%	34%
Percentage of buildings classified as “Low”	39%	35%
Percentage of buildings classified as “Medium”	23%	25%
Percentage of buildings classified as “High”	15%	4%
Percentage of buildings classified as “Very High”	2%	2%

Approximately 40% of the buildings identified exhibit a "Low" S-gradient intensity classification, indicating a relatively diminished susceptibility to damage. Conversely, a minority of buildings demonstrate "High/Very High" S-gradient intensities. The difference only in “High” class can be linked to the lack of CSK dataset which caused fewer MPs in the defined area (southern Barcelona) in CSK. Consequently, the extent of building identification in this area is correspondingly lower. EGMS-S1, on the other hand, detects more buildings classified as "High" intensity within the same region. In terms of building uniformity, it's notable that the majority of these detected buildings are identical in both datasets. This is despite the fact that some buildings are identified solely by

one dataset. This could be explained by a multitude of factors such as differences in imaging resolution, frequency bands, and errors in the PSI processing chain (Solari, et al. 2017).

Figure 5. Differential deformation maps for buildings in Barcelona, using data from EGMS-S1 and PSIG-CSK, respectively. Damage potential buildings are coloured by the S-gradient intensity classes.

In the subsequent examples, we look into four specific zones corresponding to the numbered areas depicted in Figure 5 and compared the outcomes.

In our initial example, we examine Zone 1 as delineated in Figure 5, where we specifically look at four separate structures located within Barcelona airport. A detailed investigation of the displacement map depicted in Figure 2 reveals that this particular area is undergoing a significant deformation, characterized by subsidence, with a cumulative displacement up to -40 mm/yr over a span of five years. The primary cause behind this phenomenon is likely the extensive extraction of groundwater within this vicinity (Gao, et al. 2022). Figures 6a through 6d illustrated the detailed process undertaken to generate the differential deformation map to obtain the vulnerability of airport buildings. The final map reveals a range of S-gradient intensities, from "*Low*" to "*Medium*," signifying the potential risk of damage. Notably, the maximum S-gradient values recorded for the airport's main building stand at 0.12 and 0.11 $\text{mm} \times \text{yr}^{-1} \times \text{m}^{-1}$ in the EGMS-S1 and PSIG-CSK datasets, respectively. In terms of comparing two datasets, note that the observed difference in a building (upper left) corresponds to the number of active MPs within a specific polygon, which is used in the S-gradient computation. Despite this difference, both datasets agree on identifying buildings that are vulnerable to damage.

Figure 6. Overview of creating Differential deformation map in Barcelona airport area. a) PSI displacement, b) velocity interpolation, c) gradient computation and d) differential deformation maps. The differential deformation map depicts "Low" and "Medium" S-gradient intensities in airport buildings. The left four figures represent the data acquired by EGMS-S1, whereas the right four figures show data from PSIG-CSK.

In our second example, we shift our focus to Zone 2 as delineated in Figure 5, which pertains to construction activities undertaken in El Prat de Llobregat, where an underground car park was built from 2017 to 2019. Figures 7a through 7d meticulously document the steps involved in the Differential Deformation Map procedure, leveraging data from two distinct datasets. The presence of a noticeable S-gradient of deformation in buildings can be observed in figure 7c. also Figure 7d shows that two identical buildings fall under the "Medium" and "High" classes of S-gradient

intensity (on the upper side of the street). Specifically, the maximum S-gradient values for the orange-coloured building (“High”) are quite similar, recorded as 0.27 and 0.25 $\text{mm}\times\text{yr}^{-1}\times\text{m}^{-1}$ in the EGMS-S1 in the PSIG-CSK, respectively. Conversely two distinct buildings were detected individually at the bottom side of the street and fall into the “Medium” categorization with relatively similar S-gradient values of 0.18 $\text{mm}\times\text{yr}^{-1}\times\text{m}^{-1}$ in EGMS-S1 and 0.20 $\text{mm}\times\text{yr}^{-1}\times\text{m}^{-1}$ in PSIG-CSK. Both distinct buildings underwent a validation process, that included a field survey.

Figure 7. Overview of creating Differential deformation map in El Prat de Llobregat zone where the underground construction activities took place. a) PSI displacement, b) velocity interpolation, c) gradient computation and d) differential deformation maps. The differential deformation map shows “Medium” and “High” S-gradient intensities in surrounding buildings. The left four figures represent the data acquired by EGMS-S1, whereas the right four figures show data from PSIG-CSK.

The surveys provided real evidence of damage, such as the presence of cracks. In the following section, we will discuss more detailed about validation process.

When analysing Figure 7, specifically focusing on the PSIG-CSK, a notable observation arises: certain additional buildings were exclusively identified by PSIG-CSK, with no corresponding detection in EGMS-S1. These buildings exhibit S-gradient intensities ranging from "*Low*" to "*Medium*," and they are most likely influenced by construction activities along this street. The disparities in building detection can be attributed to the higher resolution provided by PSIG-CSK. The subsequent analyses, focusing on zones 3 and 4 as delineated in Figure 5, provide examples of cases where buildings were exclusively detected by a single dataset. The first one pertains to the harbours of Barcelona, which are susceptible to a variety of deformations induced by natural processes such as sedimentation, compaction, and erosion, as well as human activities such as the construction of new infrastructure (Vanneste, et al. 2014). Figure 8 provides a comprehensive visualization of the differential deformation map process, including PSI displacement, velocity interpolation, gradient computation, and the generation of a differential deformation map utilizing two distinct datasets. Notably, Figure 8d highlights that the majority of buildings were identified by both datasets, exhibiting a "*Low*" S-gradient intensity level. However, a few smaller structures were exclusively detected by PSIG-CSK, similarly a phenomenon attributed to its better spatial resolution. In contrast, Figure 9 displays the differential deformation map of Barcelona port, highlighting that EGMS-S1 has detected a higher quantity of buildings in comparison to PSIG-CSK. The failure of PSIG-CSK to identify some structures in particular locations, such as the upper zone, could be attributed to the lack of PSIG-CSK images. The temporal intervals between consecutive dates of PSIG-CSK images are approximately 32 days on average, while between 2018 and 2019, this range reaches up to 168, taking into account all 50 images (look at Table

1). This variation in temporal baselines results in low coherence and sparse distribution of MPs in particular areas.

Figure 8. Overview of creating Differential deformation map in Barcelona harbor where the number of detected buildings with PSIG-CSK is higher than EGMS-S1. a) PSI displacement, b) velocity interpolation, c) gradient computation and d) differential deformation maps. The left four figures represent the data acquired by EGMS-S1, whereas the right four figures show data from PSIG-CSK.

Figure 9. Overview of creating Differential deformation map in Barcelona port where the number of detected buildings with EGMS-S1 is higher than PSIG-CSK. a) PSI displacement, b) velocity interpolation, c) gradient computation and d) differential deformation maps. The left four figures represent the data acquired by EGMS-S1, whereas the right four figures show data from PSIG-CSK.

4.2. S-gradient Orientation

It is worth considering the orientation of the S-gradient, which plays an important role in understanding deformation patterns. In fact, S-gradient orientation can be used to examine the direction of cracks, shifts, or distortions in building elements. In order to look into the S-gradient orientation in one of the proposed areas, Figure 10 focuses on the cases shown in Figure 7. It illustrates the arrows, which represent the orientation of the maximum S-gradient of deformation for each building. Almost all the arrows are directed towards the construction street that is marked

by a pink line. This suggested that buildings on both side of street lean toward the center of the street.

Figure 10. A plot of buildings surrounding a construction site and S-gradient orientation which is shown by purple arrow on each building. All arrows point toward the street that has deformation due to underground construction activities. The street is shown by a pink line.

4.3. Field Survey

One important assessment method is to conduct a field survey to evaluate the condition of identified structures. The survey's primary goal is to locate and evaluate any structural cracks or fractures. In this work, a survey was performed over certain buildings in the underground construction zone of El Prat de Llobregat (zone 2 in Figure 5). All buildings in the vicinity of the mentioned street were examined and two of them were selected as examples in Figure 11, namely Building No.1 and Building No.3, which have "Medium" and "High" levels of S-gradient intensity, respectively. Figure 11a shows Building No.3 which not only reveals the presence of some cracks but also indicates a visible movement of the building which leans toward the street when viewed from the side (see Figure 11, middle). The distance observed between two neighbouring structures serves as good evidence of this occurrence, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive understanding of the building's response to differential deformation. By contrast, Figure 11b illustrates building No.1, where a few small cracks were detected on both sides of

the building. Note that these buildings were observed from four perspectives (front, back, left, and right, with the red colour indicating the view direction in Figure 11). It is important to acknowledge that detecting signs of damage on a building's exterior, particularly cracks, might be difficult due to renovations and wall painting that can hide them. Additionally, the type of materials for the exterior surface of a building can impact the simplicity of crack detection. To comprehend the underlying reasons for the cracks and movement, additional information, such as geotechnical assessments, structural analyses, recording of the building's history records, and construction materials, may be considered.

Figure 11. Examples of field survey evidence and cracks in El Prat de Llobregat. Left plots depict building No.1 with a “Medium” intensity class. Minor cracks were discovered in this structure on back and left sides, which is shown by red colour. Middle and right plots depict building No.3 with a “High” intensity class across two perspectives (left and right). Some cracks and a distance between two adjacent blocks were discovered.

5. Conclusion

EGMS provides reliable and consistent information on ground movement across national boundaries. This service allows for utilizing displacement maps on both national and local scales as well as monitoring individual buildings.

In this work, we have presented a methodology to detect and categorize potential damage classes for buildings by analyzing differential deformation. This tool allows the generation of the building differential deformation map, which supports the identification of buildings and urban structures that could be at risk of damage due to differential movements. The application of this tool starting from two different input datasets (EGMS-S1 and PSIG-S1) has shown that it can be applied to DInSAR displacement maps with different characteristics in terms of processing approach or spatial resolution. The analysis of the tool's preliminary performances was conducted in the municipality of Barcelona. A building differential deformation map has been created, and all detected buildings have been categorized into 5 classes that indicate the level of intensity of deformation S-gradient. The incorporation of S-gradient uncertainty is the key factor in designing a classification system. By conducting Monte Carlo simulations with random errors applied to both the displacement velocity and the position of MPs, an S-gradient standard deviation of $0.05 \text{ mm} \times \text{yr}^{-1} \times \text{m}^{-1}$ was estimated.

To analyse the outcomes of this study, two types of datasets were used: displacement maps from EGMS-S1 and PSIG-CSK. Both datasets span the years 2017 through 2021 and they are in ASC geometry. In total, 149 and 155 buildings were detected as at-risk buildings by EGMS-S1 and PSIG-CSK, respectively. By comparing the results obtained from EGMS-S1 and PSIG-CSK datasets, valuable insights can be gained regarding the detection and characterization of buildings. Examples include the underground construction activity in El Prat de Llobregat, subsidence in the Barcelona airport area, and deformation in the harbour area. The majority of identified buildings

are identical by the two datasets; however, some buildings have been identified only in one of the two datasets. To validate the proposed methodology, a field survey was conducted to observe any visible damage such as cracks on the walls. In the construction zone of El Prat de Llobregat, some buildings have slight cracks on the exterior, and one building leans towards the street, as evidenced by the distance between two neighbouring structures.

The differential deformation map serves as the first layer of information required for an in-depth analysis and risk assessment. By utilizing this map, beneficiaries can improve their ability to assure building safety and stability, contributing to a more comprehensive awareness of structural issues and supporting effective risk mitigation procedures.

Future research may need additional geotechnical assessment, structural analysis, and historical records, to gain a comprehensive knowledge of the components that contribute to cracks and deformation in buildings. Incorporating continuous monitoring and temporal analysis, particularly given the annual updates of EGMS data, can be valuable. Continuous monitoring helps in the early detection of emergent concerns by allowing the discovery of patterns or trends in structure behaviour over time. Another future work consideration is the incorporation of a reliability index for each building, inspired by the proven effectiveness of the Quality Index of Active Deformation Areas (ADAs) in the Barra et al. 2017 approach. This approach enhances the precision of deformation differential measurement, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the potential damage risk for buildings and improved risk assessment capabilities.

6. Contribution statement

Saeedeh Shahbazi: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - first draft, Visualization, Writing - review & editing. **Anna Barra:** Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, and Writing - review & editing. **Qi Gao:** Investigation,

Resources, Writing - review & editing. **Michele Crosetto**: Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Writing - review & editing

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8. Data availability

Data can be downloaded through EGMS webpage: <https://egms.land.copernicus.eu/>.

Building data can be accessible here: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/#map=6/40.01/-2.49>.

The source code used in this work is available at <https://github.com/saeedehshahbazi/detecting-differential-deformation.git>.

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